

Public Smoking: It is Time for a National Ban.

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Introduction

The mass production of Cigarettes in the United States likely began around the 1860s. Since then, the overall engineering of cigarettes has remained chiefly static, aside from a few minor changes. Today's Cigarettes consist of a filter and tipping paper near the inhalation point, cigarette paper, tobacco filler, and various other additives at the location where the cigarette is burned. The filter and inhalation holes are designed to encourage smokers to inhale more deeply into their lungs, leading to maximum absorption of dangerous chemicals in the additives and tobacco filler (*CDC, 2022*). Cigarettes became popular among Civil War troops; the packaging made them more convenient for battle conditions and easy to distribute among soldiers. The popularity of cigarettes rapidly increased until they became mainstream around 1900. The use of cigarettes in the United States went unabated until the 1950s, when smoking was linked to lung cancer. By then, cigarettes were firmly integrated into American Culture, mainly due to tobacco companies' aggressive advertising and lobbying efforts. While the first state-wide public smoking restriction was implemented in 1973 in Arizona (*CDC, 2022*), the link between secondhand smoke (SHS) and the risk of lung cancer was not confirmed until 1986. Since then, evidence of harm from SHS has proliferated, and 27 other states have enacted some form of public smoking restriction. (American Lung Association, n.d.) In addition to the increase in medical and scientific evidence supporting the regulation of public smoking, court cases and legal findings over the last fifty years have revealed a compelling basis for legislative action. Additionally, the concern over Health Care spending has reached a flash point, with annual healthcare spending increasing from 7.8% of GDP in 1973 to 18.3% in 2021 despite GDP per capita increasing by 10,000% (*Macrotrends, 2023*)

This paper proposes sweeping federal legislation restricting smoking in public places based on the overwhelming evidence of the harmful effects of secondhand smoke, the high economic costs to taxpayers, and the government's constitutional obligation to protect public health.

Evidence for legislative action

Smoking has been linked to several top causes of death in the United States. Specific areas of concern are its strong causal relationship with Heart Disease, Lung Cancer, and COPD (CDC, 2022). The evidence for Smoking's link to disease has steadily grown over the past seventy years; however, regarding Secondhand Smoke, the evidence has only recently reached critical mass within the past twenty or thirty years. While Direct Smoking and other factors still retain a large share of the disease burden, SHS (Secondhand Smoke) represents an impressive 22% of the disease burden concerning Lung Cancer, Heart Disease, and COPD in North American countries (CDC, 2022). The potential for harm is exceptionally high among children, where even relatively small but not uncommon amounts of smoke exposure have been found to increase the chances of developing asthma and a decrease in overall lung health later in life. Moreover, recent research indicates that small amounts of smoke exposure have a cumulative effect on lung and heart health over long periods (*Kaufman et al., 2010*). This poses a concern for individuals often exposed to SHS in passing. This includes locations such as at the entrance to apartment or office buildings, which are often hot spots among smokers due to the convenience, legality, and shelter provided at the entrances of most buildings. In addition to the human cost of SHS, there is a substantial financial cost. In 2020, the United States spent a combined \$292 Billion on Lung Cancer, COPD, and heart disease-related healthcare.

Efficacy of Public Smoking Bans

Concerns regarding the efficacy of Public Smoking Restrictions have been raised continuously since the first restrictions were implemented in the US State of Arizona in 1973. One of the common concerns is that preventing smokers from smoking in parks and buildings, along with removing public smoking areas, has pushed smokers onto the sidewalks and near the entrances of buildings. While the notion that smokers have been forced into more condensed areas that are less convenient for both the smoker and passersby, the legislation that is the subject of this report is a National, Sweeping, Public Smoking ban that would not allow smoking within so many feet of a building. There are also concerns that public smoking legislation pushes smokers inside, where children or pregnant individuals will be at even greater risk of exposure - while this is undoubtedly an alarming and valid concern, the benefits of this proposed legislation would far outweigh the risks, and, at the same time, it is crucial to recognize that such negligence would need to be the target of separate legislation, which has already been proposed, stating that SHS is Child Abuse (Goldstein, 2015). The Statistical efficacy of Public Smoking bans has been proven repeatedly in medical literature, with bans on smoking in Government offices and workplaces found to reduce the odds of smoking by 14% overall and up to 28% in some cases. It is essential to recognize that the legislation proposed by this article would be significantly broader than previously studied legislation and that the efficacy of broad legislation is expected to be higher than that of the current piece-wise approach (Bird et al., 2020).

Legal Basis.

Since the inception of smoking restrictions, the legality of such regulations has been hotly debated, specifically, the implications of the Third, Fourth, Fifth, and Fourteenth amendment to the United States Constitution, which guarantee a right to privacy in the home, protection against

unreasonable searches, protection of private information, and the guarantee of equal protection of rights, respectively. A Review of case law over the last 50 years provides strong evidence for the legality of Public Smoking Restrictions. In the case *City of North Miami v. Kurtz*, it was found that Smokers do not have a legitimate expectation of privacy as smokers are constantly required to reveal whether they smoke, such as when obtaining a smoking or non-smoking hotel room or rental car (*Casetext*, 1995). In *CLASH Inc. v. City of New York*, it was found that the First Amendment places no protections on individuals' right to smoke, drink, eat, fight, etc., despite the assertion that such behaviors may be associated with protected social events, similarly, the Freedom of speech does not protect the production or consumption of child pornography, and the freedom of religion does not preclude compliance with child labor laws. The case also discusses the Right to Equal Protection guaranteed under the Fourteenth Amendment and finds that, unlike policy regarding gay marriage, legislation surrounding smoking does not establish a classification, and therefore there is no identification requiring equal protection under the fourteenth amendment (*Casetext*, 2004)

Recommendations and Conclusion

There is a superfluous amount of Scientific, Medical, Economic, and Legal evidence for implementing Anti-Smoking legislation to protect American Citizens from SHS exposure and undue financial burden. This paper recommends the implementation of the Federally Legislated National Public Smoking Law, in which Smoking is prohibited in all public places, businesses, Multi-Family Residential properties, Public Parks, Mixed-Use Buildings, Public Transportation, and Facilities, within 15 feet of any entrance to the aforementioned buildings, within 50 feet of a public park, within 100 feet of Healthcare, Educational, Childcare, or Community health clinics, and at Farmers Markets or Open Food Markets, with required standardized signage. An Example

of the Proposed Legislation can be found at:

[https://www.scribd.com/document/638537761/Smoking-Legislation.](https://www.scribd.com/document/638537761/Smoking-Legislation)

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